

The role and importance of competitive intelligence in competitive dynamics: Two exploratory surveys

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Abstract: The aim of this paper is to present the findings of two competitive intelligence (CI) surveys that will be used in a broader study on CI methods and applications in the strategic management subfield of competitive dynamics. The first study is a broad, exploratory survey among the members of Strategic and Competitive Intelligence Professionals (SCIP) organization concerning attitudes about the use of different CI applications within their firms. For the second, more focused study we conducted structured interviews with managers about their use of CI in a fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) sector in Italy. We discuss our findings and present CI challenges in contemporary management practice: namely, the managerial shift of CI, the importance of knowledge and data availability for SMEs, and the role of social media.

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Introduction

Competitive intelligence (CI) is a crucial activity for firms engaged in competitive marketplaces. CI is a business system that provides information for reducing market uncertainty and aiding decision-makers in achieving a competitive advantage for their firms. Many complex and simultaneous CI processes can be used to scan and analyze a firm's competitive environment and stakeholders. In addition, it can be employed to gather systematic intelligence about brands, consumers and competitors to improve the quality of decision making. For instance, M-Brain conducts regular bi-annual Global Market Intelligence Surveys covering 469 large firms in 50 countries and 20 industries. They've found that almost 85% of firms have developed formal and systematic CI operations. The M-Brain survey also shows that return on investment (ROI) is higher for 62% of these firms (M-brain White Paper, 2015). Prescott (1999) asserts that paramount to CI is the development of a business system that provides timely, action-oriented implications for managers. From practitioners' points of view, CI is not the information *per se*, but the functional information system that answers specific questions (IMA, 2016). The role of CI – to help managers anticipate competitors' moves and improve the quality of their decision-making processes – exceeds a mere data collection effort. Without CI, a firm ignores (at its peril!) the competitive interplay between high-impact players and resources, which is the essence of competitive dynamics (IMA, 2016).

Given the importance of CI, we have conducted two brief studies: the first on the use of CI across multiple industries, and the second on qualitative interviews with managers in the Italian fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) industry. We developed these two exploratory studies as part of a broader research project examining CI and its effects on competitive dynamics at the strategic level. The topics our exploratory studies examined include: the use (or non-use) of a formal CI process, the nature of CI information gathered, the tools used in gathering CI, how the CI system helps the firm in decision making, how the CI system improves the speed of the firm's reaction to marketplace events, and how the CI system improves understanding of consumers and competitors. Our results should be useful for practitioners interested in learning more about what others are doing with CI.

The first study, conducted with the help of SCIP, investigates why CI is important. The second study involved semi-structured interviews with five Italian managers concerning their use of CI in the FMCG industry sectors. This study attempts to illuminate how CI contributes to competitive dynamics in the FMCG industry.

Study 1: SCIP members' survey

The aim of Study No. 1 is to offer evidence explaining *why* CI is important through a SCIP member survey. We collected 58 answers in the period of November 2017 and January 2018. First, we asked if the respondents' firms use some type of formal CI system – e.g., a formal department, in-house analysis of competitors, market research reports from companies like ACNielsen or GfK, or have other formal procedures for gathering CI; 88.68% answered Yes, while 11.32% answered No. We also wanted to know how their firms collect CI data (see Figure 1). Multiple answers were possible.

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According to our respondents, 42.86% have a formal department within their firm, 82.14% use in-house analysis, 64.29% use market research analysis, 3.57% have no information about CI activities, and 32.14% use some other means to collect CI data. In the last group, one firm has a business intelligence manager within the marketing department, and two firms use social media analysis. These findings show that CI activities are widely recognized and practiced in firms that are part of the SCIP sample, and that in-house analysis and informal data collection are the dominant forms of CI. These high percentages are not surprising because respondents are SCIP members who are familiar with CI activities. Interestingly, although methods of data collection and analysis vary widely across our SCIP respondents, only unstructured forms (informal and in-house analyses) are dominant CI practices.

We also wanted to know: how managers compare their CI system to the systems of competitors, what are viewed as the most important pieces of CI information, how the CI system helps in decision making, and how the use of CI improves decision making.

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Relative comparisons of business practices are important in managerial practice. We asked managers to compare their own CI practices with those of their competitors, and these results are presented in Table 1. The respondents strongly agree that CI system is a benefit for a firm, help them to better understand their competitors, allows reacting faster, and being successful in the industry. However, the respondents have more neutral opinions about the capacity of CI activities to anticipate the speed of reaction and competitors' moves.

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We chose the most informative respondents for the qualitative analysis of our SCIP study, which we present in Table 2. These managers work in mining, high tech, semiconductor, medical research, consulting, and software industries, and have extensive professional experience. We focused on their answers to several key CI questions:

1. Are formal CI processes used, and what CI tools are most helpful in gathering data beyond formal department or syndicated services?
2. What are the important pieces of CI information?
3. How does the CI system help in decision making?
4. Does the CI system improve the speed and type of reaction to competitive threats, and how?
5. How does the CI system improve understanding of consumers and competitors.

The SCIP survey respondents indicated they use various CI tools beyond the formal department or syndicated services, such as monitoring social media, use of specialized software for products aggregation, consultants, and similar. It was found that the firm's industry determines the nature of CI. The software companies are mostly interested in future trends across channels and competitors overview. The managers in mining and metals are mostly interested in the regulatory environment, employment data and changes in volume sales. On the other hand, service firms are more interested in understanding the strategic environment overall.

The CI activities are very important for improving the decision making. The respondents said it allows them to better target prospective sales based on geography, industrial sector and market data. In addition, the decision-making is based on data and facts rather than hunches that help in a better understanding of market changes, future trends, and the necessary speed in these processes. According to the respondents, CI is crucial in understanding consumers and rivals. For instance, CI helps in developing a cohesive sales strategy, may help identify blind spots in the market, and may provide an early read of competitors' speed of product launch. In addition, CI has an important role on a brand level because it helps in the creation of new brands, provides a clear strategy to rejuvenate a brand, and may properly re-position a brand against late entrants to the market.

Study 2: Italian FMCG managers

In addition to the survey of why CI is important, we want to show in Study #2 how CI is relevant and valuable for managers in the FMCG industry. We conducted in-depth, semi-structured interviews

with marketing and brand managers who sell products into the Italian groceries marketplace. From these interviews, we can offer unattributed quotations from business managers on how they perceive CI, how they use CI activities daily, and the challenges they see in using CI.

The data collection comprised 5 in-depth interviews with marketing and brand managers who produce grocery products that sell in the Italian market. We used managers from diverse firm types (food production, milk, juices, mineral water, and wine), which allows us to make comparisons between different uses of CI across the grocery sector and provides a more generalizable interpretation of our findings (cf. Creswell, 2007).

The in-depth interviews in Table 3 addressed topics concerning: the use of a formal CI system in the firm, the nature of CI information gathered, the use of CI in decision making, the types of tools or syndicated services employed in gathering market intelligence, how firms use CI in choosing speed of response to rivals' actions, and how firms can better understand consumers and rivals using CI. We pre-tested the interview guide for clarity using three senior scholars who specialize in qualitative research and in-depth interview methodologies. After their comments, we made minor wording changes.

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CI challenges from a managerial perspective

The common themes across the diverse companies in our exploratory study with the SCIP members and structured interviews with managers in the Italian grocery supply market are as follows. First, CI use may be shifting from standardized market information about rivals to more customized knowledge about customers. Second, customer knowledge and data availability are important for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). And third, social media is an important source of knowledge about markets and rivals for SMEs. We next address each of these themes in more detail.

A) A managerial shift for CI?

One typical application of CI in managerial practice and scholarly work is the use of syndicated data (i.e., from Nielsen, GfK, or similar sources) that provides micro and/or macro quantitative explanations of consumers' and competitors' actions through standardized consumer and retail panel datasets. These data are expensive, however, and are standardized for the industry sector, geographical area or specific type of consumers. These data are limited by a pre-defined structure that can restrict the scope of knowledge obtained due to the pre-definition of the available variables. Comments from managers of FMCG manufacturers suggest that there may a desire for CI to go beyond the use of

syndicated information about markets and competitors and toward more targeted inquiries on consumers and their behavior.

“We would like to have this kind of analysis more structured. Ok? For me, Nielsen [analysis] is not enough to have a good analysis [of the market]. This system [competitive intelligence] could be more structured. Ok? Now, it is conducted with good sense [of managers], but [in future] we have to decide what to do. Now this is the problem [the competitive intelligence system performance]; this we have to understand in the near future. In the long term, when our firm is going to evolve, I would like to structure [competitive intelligence] better.”

- So, you want to improve your competitive intelligence system?

“Yes. In the future, [competitive intelligence system] will not be about rivals, but consumers.” (ALPHA WATER)

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“...business [is] broadly unaware of the difference between customer insight and competitive intelligence.” (SCIP Respondent #8)

B) Customer knowledge and data availability are important for SMEs

The importance of customer knowledge and data availability for SMEs is not yet fully addressed in the CI literature. Smolka (2016) asserts that the problem of abundant market data and lack of managerial insight occurs because data is not in itself an answer for SME managers wishing to make decisions. SMEs often have limited resources and scopes of business activity. This implies that SMEs need knowledge about the specific area of competition (geographical, market trends in specific product sub-sectors, the behavior of direct rivals, etc.) that cannot be covered by standardized syndicated services or macro data from industry reports.

“We usually find statistical information and we [use it] in this business intelligence software (i.e. Qlik Sense), and match it also with market penetration and market share ratio. For example, we use ISTAT, which is the Italian Statistical Institute, and they make statistics on alcohol consumption. We can have this kind of data about regions [in Italy] and we can “translate” this data on our market penetration. So, the market share [information] we can have it from the internal data that we filter with this business intelligence software, then we mix it with external data like ISTAT. This kind of software also has the market data, but we usually do not use [it] because we do not use such a huge national

data. We only need a few information that we can find directly on the Internet.”
(BETA WINE)

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“It is really important [CI system] because all our decisions are in function of this data. For example, if our competitors produce wine with characteristics similar to ours and sell this wine for 10 euros, it is impossible for us to sell it for 20 euros. So, data and the analysis of the market... the system of information is the base how we make our decisions. This system is very, very important for us. So, the information we gather affect our decision [making].”

- What are you typically looking for? Quantities? Price? What else?

“Quantity, price, type of wine, characteristics of wine. So, we try to taste other [competitors’] wines, to understand if that wine is similar to us. Also, the trademark, because if that trademark is well known it is positioned in different segments of the market. There is a lot of specific information that is important for us to understand how to run our business.” (ALPHA WINE)

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“CI is used not only to take action and for decision making but for education. Having a workforce well-educated about the competitors is the best competitive advantage.” (SCIP Respondent #15)

C) The role of social media

The importance of social media tools like Facebook and LinkedIn was supported in our data, especially for smaller firms. The rapid development of social media and various technological platforms has produced a tremendous amount of firm-related data and consumer-generated content that are freely available for data mining. The managerial literature (e.g. Calof, Sewdass, & Arcos, 2017; Scacchi, 2017) also recognize the growing importance of the Internet and technology for gathering information and communicating CI benefits. To improve competitive advantage, firms must be able to distinguish the valuable “nuggets” of information that are scattered in a large and often disorganized digital field.

“...we are engaged in social marketing, to better understand the consumer. [For instance,] Facebook! We talk a lot with our consumers. [On] our page, water speaks with a consumer.” (ALPHA WATER)

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“Internet is the first [source of] information. For instance, specialized [web] pages as well as social media such as LinkedIn, Facebook; there are some opinion makers and consultants that explain how to make these decisions and how to position the product.” (ALPHA WINE)

“Those are [CI tools] – Internet pages and social networks like Facebook. It is not easy to exchange the information. There are no specific [information] tools for wine producers.” (ALPHA WINE)

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”... my and firm objective is to obtain and filter the information from social media and translate it to marketing information, of course. Now, we are not using yet..” (BETA WINE)

In addition to the interviews, the importance of social media was also recognized by some survey respondents. So, the survey and the interviews clearly show that managers are using CI and they are dependent on data that provides knowledge about market trends and rivals’ actions. Beyond the aforementioned market trends and themes, application of CI in daily practice provides information and knowledge about the rivals’ past behavior and (likely) future competitive maneuvers. Following the findings from our studies, we distinguish between the “Market information” and “Business knowledge” as crucial dimensions in managerial application of CI and present them in Table 4.

Table 4: The differences and orientation of Market information and Business knowledge in the CI application

	Time orientation	Type of decision	Speed of decision	Data type	Syndicated data
Market information	Short-term	Tactical	Fast and limited	Standardized	Sufficient
Business knowledge	Long-term	Strategic	Slow and complex	Customized	Insufficient

The primary role of market information in the CI application is to constitute a sufficient basis for decision making about the speed and volume of competitive actions in the market. A firm is in need of market information to make short-term and mostly tactical decisions such as changes in price

policies, adjustments in market share outputs, responses to the new advertising campaign of a rival, and similar. Typical CI users of market information are big companies that already have experience and knowledge about their most important rivals and their typical market behavior.

Business knowledge enables new judgment and supports strategic decisions about market rules, players, and the marketing program. Knowledge is necessary for a company to make long-term and mostly strategical decisions (i.e. consumer preferences and trends, new brand introductions, changes in the brand portfolio, etc.). For instance, making a deep analysis of rivals and their market behavior based only on syndicated data provides limited and biased knowledge about rivals' business strategies. Standardized syndicated data are insufficient to make strategic level decisions and to understand the market and consumer trends. This is the case because these data are pre-defined by the general research task, standardized consumer or retail panel modeling and the scope of research that is limited by the number of variables and costs of obtaining the data that may accommodate a typical user of syndicated data (a firm). For instance, SMEs need customized knowledge about a very specific problem they face or market rules about the market they want to enter.

Conclusions

This paper has presented the findings of two CI surveys, which are the part of the broader study on CI in the field of competitive dynamics. The first study is an exploratory study among the members of SCIP organization and their attitudes about the application of CI activities within their firms and market. The second study presents the structured interviews with managers to obtain unattributed quotations about the use of CI in the Italian FMCG sector. During our research and analysis we have identified the common themes across these diverse companies; namely - the managerial shift of CI, the acquisition of knowledge for SME, and the importance of social media. We argue that crucial dimensions in a managerial application of CI are the Market information and Business knowledge.

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Figures

Figure 1: CI Data Collected by Respondents' Firms

Tables

Table 1: Comparison of our CI system to competitors

	Strongly disagree			Neither			Strongly agree
... is a benefit to our company	10.71%	3.57%	3.57%	14.29%	10.71%	17.86%	39.29%
... helps us to better understand our competitors	3.57%	10.71%	0.00%	10.71%	14.29%	28.57%	32.14%
... helps us to better understand our customers	3.57%	17.86%	0.00%	14.29%	17.86%	21.43%	25.00%
... allows us to react faster to competitors' moves	7.14%	3.57%	3.57%	28.57%	14.29%	17.86%	25.00%
... allows us to better anticipate competitors' moves	10.71%	3.57%	0.00%	21.43%	28.57%	14.29%	21.43%
... makes executive decision making more efficient and timely	3.57%	7.14%	3.57%	21.43%	21.43%	21.43%	21.43%
... helps me be successful in my job	0.00%	3.57%	7.14%	25.00%	7.14%	25.00%	32.14%
... is important to success in this industry	0.00%	14.29%	0.00%	7.14%	7.14%	32.14%	39.29%

Table 2: SCIP Members' Quotations

	Scip #25	Scip #21	Scip #20	Scip #15	Scip #14
Description	Mining industry, 6 years of experience in the field	High Tech, 25+ years of experience in the field	Semiconductor, 20 years of experience in the field	Consulting, 10 years of experience in the field	Medical research, 39 years of experience in the field
Tools in use, beyond formal department or syndicated services (Q3)	Business intelligence manager within the marketing department			Social Web Listening	competitive intelligence aggregation product; consultants
Pieces of CI (Q5)	Regulatory decisions, bid award outcomes, and employment data	The most important pieces of competitive intelligence are insights and recommendations; however, sales thinks battlecards are the most important.	volume sales, i.e. growth trends, changes in the market, etc.	Strategic Reviews Real-time Early Warning Opportunity System WarGames	...include what our customers say about competitors, analysis of the capabilities of competitors and news
Process of decision making (Q6)	Allows us to target prospective sales based on geographic, industry, and market data. Also aligns with our M&A goals.	It is based on data and facts rather than hunches.	Helps us to better understand market movement and direction	Providing support to both tactical and strategic decision-making	supports new product development, current product improvements, product launches, product pricing, sales talking points, product positioning, marketing and customer engagement, annual strategic visioning, educating product managers and sales, informs new business relationships and new licensing
Understanding the consumers and rivals (Q7)	Helped us better understand a specific organization to acquire and develop a cohesive sales strategy.	There was a product launch that depended on competitive insights. The recommendation that came out of it was that the market was over-saturated and it did not make sense to launch the	CI isn't a formal process for us, it's part of regular day2day activity, so understanding our markets always helps in improving decisions.	WarGame to enter a new market. It helped in identifying blindspots of top management and align the organization to design and	CI helped us create the best new product to counter the current two big products in the market. Based on a year in the market, we have learned that our product sales has

		product. The company did not listen and launched the product anyway.		deliver a winning strategy in that market to this day	negatively impacted at least one competitor as a result
Comments (Q8)		I would like to see CI viewed as strategic, but at the moment it is more tactical and is more reactive when it should be proactive.	CI is not yet a formal process for us, though we are changing that. We are slow to make decisions and I believe having a formal CI function will help improve our knowledge sets and make us more efficient.	CI Is the umbrella concept that includes all forms of intelligence from business to strategic to artificial intelligence	CI is used not only to take action and for decision making but for education. Having a workforce well-educated about the competitors is the best competitive advantage. All our competitive knowledge is curated and managed by the CI manager using a Sharepoint site to maximize access and use 24/7

	Scip #4	Scip #8	Scip #12	Scip #6	Scip #5
Description	Software industry, 1 year of experience in the field	Telecommunications, 20 years of experience in the field	Technology	Cosmetics	Software industry
Tools in use, beyond formal department or syndicated services (Q3)		social media			Software
Pieces of CI (Q5)	Competitor Overviews	Would not say it is input pieces but output-based outcomes on a range of here and now topics that steer a range alternative future states	Analyses and market insights	Consumer behavior	Being able to connect the dots across channels - website, pricing, reviews, etc.
Process of decision making (Q6)	Gives a larger picture to a single decision. Can find	Regular review of external dynamic, stress test what we	analyzing relevant topics of information	Speed and correct decision making	Helps drive priorities and respond to opportunities and threats.

	smaller details that were unknown before.	are doing, make the right choices to benefit tomorrow			
Understanding the consumers and rivals (Q7)	Acquisition, helped understand what competitive 'responsibilities' we'd need to take care of i.e. competitors in the space, competitive share of market, competitor growth & movement, etc.	CI planning used against range of market entry tactics for new entrant, early read of speed of launch to confirm range of scenarios had planned for	Gained a better understanding of our USP	Rejuvenate brand	Ran a sales and marketing promotion based on a competitor's product end of life.
Comments (Q8)	Very high use within presales & sales	...business [is] broadly unaware of the difference between customer insight and competitive intelligence.			

Table 3: Italian Agri-food Manufacturers' CI Quotations

	Alpha Food	Alpha Water	Alpha Wine	Beta Wine	Beta food
Description	Large poultry producer	Large mineral water producer	SME, national and international wine producer	Small family business, national and regional wine producer	Large firm, national dairy producer
Pieces of CI	<p>- ...information about the price, product, advertising policy and market share. And, social and digital strategies.</p>	<p>- We use AC Nielsen to analyze retailers and grocery stores. We use Nielsen for retailers; grocery stores, big companies like Auchan, Carrefour, Conad and others. We use Nielsen to analyze our sales.</p> <p>- The most important information is how the consumer looks on our product.</p> <p>- We are looking at how to communicate [the value] of our product, so the consumer understands what he/she is buying.</p> <p>- ...we are engaged in social marketing, to better understand the consumer. [For instance,] Facebook! We talk a lot with our consumers. [On] our page, water speaks with a consumer.</p>	<p>- ...the market is changing and for that reason it is important to analyze a lot of information to make a good price and to understand what is the direction of this market, of the business</p> <p>- ...specialized [web] pages as well as social networks such as LinkedIn, Facebook; there are some opinion makers and consultants that explain how to make these decisions and how to position the product.</p> <p>- it is not easy to have good information because the lack of good consultants</p> <p>- The most important information is what type of market is assessed by competitors, what kind of products they sell in this market and what the price is.</p> <p>- Quantity, price, type of wine, characteristics of wine</p>	<p>- ...with business intelligence you can resume the analytical results by filtering it. You can choose, for example, a group of customers, their category, and then to understand which one is more interesting for my business, which one can generate the higher earnings for my firm</p> <p>- These kind of business customers distribute our products in territories. Geographical analysis is an important variable.</p>	<p>- We use this market analysis [from IRI infoscan] to check the performance of our brands in comparison to competitors' brands in different categories.</p> <p>- ...to analyze how the consumer market is performing. I mean, trends for categories.</p> <p>- ...we have other information on the dairy market, about the ingredients and this is not for the consumer analysis but [about] the trends in milk price</p>

<p>Tools or syndicated services in use</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We use the information from GfK about the markets. - We have our software, the Wizard Merchandising. This software monitors 100 sales points. It monitors the competitors' products; strategic products; important products with a value. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nielsen provides that information [about the sales in grocery stores]. And they also analyze our competitors; our Sardinian and Italian competitors - Few years ago, and have provided big results to us, we [had] sent psychologists in the market. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Those are Internet pages and social networks like Facebook. It is not easy to exchange the information. - There are no specific [information] tools for wine producers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We usually use Qlik Sense software. - We use ISTAT, it is Italian Statistical Institute, and they make statistics on alcohol consumption. We can have this kind of data about regions [in Italy] and we can "translate" this data on our market penetration. - ...software also has the market data, but we usually do not use [it] because we do not use such a huge national data. We only need a few information that we can find directly on the Internet. - ...my and firm objective is to obtain and filter the information from social medias and translate it to marketing information, of course. Now, we are not using yet. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We buy information from a company that is competitor of Nielsen. It is called "IRI infoscan" and they make and sell the same data as Nielsen. - We do not need other tools, just the [IRI] report every three months about the market trends for different categories in which we are interested in, for different regions in Italy. - I receive information on a daily basis about the global trends in dairy market. - We have the Facebook profile with more than 90.000 users...
<p>Process of decision making</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I monitor the partners of my competitors. Additional information about my competitors are the consumers, because we have the same consumers [target groups] and [this information] gives me [an opportunity] to find new consumers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We also analyse our competitors a lot. We analysed them every week by Nielsen, social media and also with interviewing - We do not follow our competitors about the price. These kinds of responses are 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data and the analysis of the market... the system of information is the base how we make our decisions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ...we can understand it [the firm potential] if we can make a discount to this customer [that] is based on data filtering of business intelligence. - We use the [indicator of] products storage level in [our] production area. We collect the weekly data on 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is important, but the decision making is made also on other information, too. For example, we know what the strategies of our competitors are, also with information that we hear, we talk with people and at the end this [competitive intelligence] is quite important as well.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am targeting different products and segments in comparison to them [rivals] - I am looking [for opportunities] to differentiate, to distinguish [my products] in comparison to them [rivals]. 	divided by two [distribution] channels.		the storage level, and we filter this data with business intelligence, and we can understand the storage flow of these products.	
Speed and type of reaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ...[CI] is important for making fast and diverse decisions regarding strategy, pricing [policies] and product assortment in comparison to them [my competitors]. It helps me to be faster and more reactive in finding new solutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Our time of reaction is really short. - We try to be always in the market. [We] do not sleep. And that help us also when our competitors make an action always to be ready to react on it. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system of business intelligence is important for us, because with this system we learnt to sell, learnt to plan our development. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ...we do not use it yet [against rivals], but I understand it is very useful mean for developing my business. - ... I think it can be useful to understand and match our strategies against rivals' strategies. We can also make a future analysis, but maybe we have no enough data to make it. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ...it is not speed at all. It [competitive intelligence] describes information that already happened. In terms of speed, doesn't help so much.
Understanding the consumers and rivals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We make ad-hoc surveys at sales points. We use these [surveys] to "feel" our consumers. - ...using these [information] to make [consumer] schemes [consumer groups], which gives me an overall look on consumers and competitors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The water is best sell in summer, but we are trying to make our marketing decisions to improve the market [performance] also in other periods of the year. - Talking to people, a lot of people by social [network] and commercial [channels]. - In future, [competitive intelligence system] will not be about rivals, but consumers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - [It is] important to analyze the position of others because we are more or less the last who arrived in the market. - ...understand the [business] policy of the others; not to make the same errors, to anticipate the moves of the others [in the market]. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ... we do not use it for rivals at the moment; but for customers, we mainly use the business intelligence for consumers analyses. We make a lot of analyses on consumers with business intelligence. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We see how our promotion performs in comparison to our rivals with the competitive intelligence system. It is very helpful, but after our actions had been made

<p>Spending on CI</p>	<p>...maximum 2% of [annual] marketing budget.</p>	<p>- Let's say 1% of marketing budget.</p> <p>- I think we could spend little bit more for research.</p>	<p>- ...if I want to quantify the value of time, it is a lot. The 90% of our time is [devoted in] studying the others [manufacturers].</p> <p>- ...more or less the 10.000 euros. We are organizing the fair and visits of the import managers from other countries.</p>	<p>- ...our expenses on business intelligence are mainly my time; the time I spent in developing this kind of analysis and about the producing our data.</p> <p>- ... it is the money variable, but we can translate it in time.</p> <p>- I would like to spend more money, but I have to talk about it with my family. I would like [to spend more], because I can understand, better than others [family members], the potential of this kind of information.</p>	<p>- ... we have the [annual] turnover of 160 million of euros and we invest less than 100 thousand of euros.</p> <p>- I think not less, for sure; but, I do not think we will have the big increase.</p>
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